

APPLE FIBRE AND HYDROXYPROPYLMETHYLCELLULOSE IN GLUTEN-FREE FORMULATIONS: FUNDAMENTAL RHEOLOGICAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Production of gluten-free bread that will match the properties of its wheat counterpart creates many challenges nowadays especially in terms of bread quality and nutritional adequacy. To address the aforementioned nutritional but also technological problems present in gluten-free bread production, dietary fibres can be applied considering their hydration and gel forming ability, textural and thickening effects. Apple fibre is an easily accessible fibre characterised by favourable soluble and insoluble fibre ratio and presence of polyphenols but is scarcely applied in gluten-free elaborations.

In the presented study a fundamental (dynamic oscillatory and creep-recovery tests) rheological approach was adopted to assess the viscoelasticity of maize-based gluten-free batters affected by different levels of apple fibre (AF) and hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC). Experiments were performed according to the Box-Behnken experimental design, with independent variables: quantity of HPMC (2, 3 and 4% on maize flour basis), quantity of AF (3, 5, and 7% on maize flour basis), and quantity of water (180, 190 and 200% on maize flour basis).

Increase in HPMC and AF content increased the values of elastic modulus inducing shifting towards solid elastic-like behaviour typical for dough. Additionally, $\tan \delta$ values were higher than one in most gluten-free formulations. Significant impact on creep and recovery parameters was associated with HPMC (changes in instantaneous and retarded elastic compliance) and water content (changes in Newtonian viscosity). In applied quantities, AF does not impair any of the analysed rheological parameters and hence it could be applied in gluten-free bread production as a functional ingredient.

Keywords: *gluten-free, apple fiber, hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, rheology*

INTRODUCTION

With increasing population suffering from the coeliac disease the demand for gluten-free (GF) products on the market steadily increases. Although food industry introduced a wide range of different GF bakery products, they often do not satisfy the celiac patients' nutritional needs. In recent years many studies have been conducted in order to find alternative flours and ingredients which will provide improved nutritional and technological quality of GF breads (Naqash et al., 2017). Hydrocolloids such as hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC) are often used as structural macropolymers capable to partially mimic gluten viscoelastic properties (Ronda et al., 2013). The GF bread enrichment with dietary fibres is also of special interest from nutritional as well as functional point of view considering that coeliac patients also encounters a significant incidence rate of other associated chronic diseases (obesity-metabolic syndrome and diabetes) (Cronin & Shanahan, 1997). Dietary fibres as ingredients have such positive properties as high water binding, holding capacity and can act as a good gelling and thickening agents (Rosell et al., 2009). Given the recognized dietary fibre health benefits (Kendall et al., 2010), fortifying bread with fibres is essential not only for wheat but also for GF breads.

As the by-product from apple juice and cider production, apple pomace represents a significant source of dietary fibres both insoluble and soluble ones with a total dietary fibre content of 78–89% on dry basis (Figuerola et al., 2005). Considering apple pomace calorie contribution of only 45 cal/100 g (Sotelo et al., 2007) and richness in polyphenols (Bai et al., 2013) apple pomace as well as derived dietary fibres could have a great potential in GF bread production. However, only a few studies have focused on apple pomace application in

GF bread production (Rocha Parra et al., 2015a) and the determination of starch–apple pomace mixtures' pasting properties (Rocha Parra et al., 2015b).

The knowledge of the dough rheological properties is essential considering that these properties are related to its gas-holding capacity, baking performance, and the products quality (Dobraszczyk & Morgenstern, 2003). Furthermore, dough rheology is also important in determining ingredient functionality in product development. In GF systems there is a lack of studies investigating the link between GF dough rheological properties and its behaviour during mechanical handling and baking. The inclusion of many ingredients in GF formulations brings some difficulties in determining their effect on rheology as well as great variations in consistency, going from batter to dough (Matos & Rosell, 2015).

With this in mind, this study aims to assess the effects of HPMC, apple fibres (AF) and water levels on GF batter fundamental rheology in terms of dynamic oscillatory and creep-recovery measurements.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Yellow maize flour (moisture 11.23%, protein 6.1%, ash 0.48% and fat 1.82% on dry basis), white sugar and salt were purchased from the local market. Maize starch (Milex doo Rumenka, Serbia), HPMC VIVAPUR[®] K4M food-grade (JRS, Rosenberg, Germany) and VITACEL[®] organic apple fibre AF 400 (JRS, Rosenberg, Germany) were used. According to suppliers' specification, the HPMC had 19-24% methoxyl content, 4-12% hydroxypropoxyl content, and AF had total, soluble and insoluble dietary fibre contents of 55%, 45%, 10% on dry basis respectively, and water binding capacity 4.5 g/g of dry sample.

This study used systematic trials based on a Box-Behnken experimental design (Table 1) to investigate the effect of independent variables amount of HPMC (2, 3, 4%), AF (3, 5, 7%) and water (180, 190, 200%) on dynamic oscillatory and creep-recovery parameters of GF model systems. Response functions of the dependent variables in terms of creep-recovery parameters (J_0 , J_{max} , and η_0) were estimated applying a second-order polynomial model given by Eq. (1) (Myers & Montgomery, 2002) using Design-Expert[®] software 7.0.0 (trial version, Stat-Ease Inc., USA):

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ij} x_i x_j \quad (1)$$

where y represents response value, β_0 is the intercept, β_i is the linear effect, β_{ii} is the squared effect, β_{ij} is the interaction effect and x_i and x_j are independent variables. Model and coefficients significance for each response was determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using a 5% significance level.

A mixture of 70 parts of yellow maize flour and 30 parts of maize starch was used for the examination of GF batter rheological properties. The basic GF formulation as % on base maize flour/maize starch mixture consisted of salt (2.5 %), refined sunflower oil (10 %) and white sugar (5 %). HPMC, AF and water were added according to the Box-Behnken experimental design. The addition of fibre was made by substituting 3, 5 and 7% of the base maize flour/maize starch mixture with AF. All dry ingredients were mixed with a 4-speed mixer (Gorenje ME 500 N, Slovenia) for 0.5 min; consequently, the appropriate amount of water was added and mixed for additional 2 min at speed 3. Refined sunflower oil was finally added while mixing at speed 3 for another 2 min. The obtained batters rheological behaviour was observed using a HAAKE RheoStress RS600 (Thermo Electron Corporation, Karlsruhe, Germany) equipped with parallel-plate geometry (60-mm diameter titanium serrated plate-PP60 Ti) with a 1-mm gap. The GF batter sample was placed between the plates and after adjustment to the 1 mm gap, the excess batter was removed. Exposed sample surface was covered with paraffin oil. All measurements were performed at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ after 180 s resting period. First, a strain sweep test was performed with a strain range of 0.1–100 Pa and a constant frequency of 1 Hz in order to identify the linear viscoelastic region for each GF batter sample. In dynamic oscillatory measurements, a constant shear stress value

previously defined within the linear viscoelastic region (between 0.1 and 1 Pa) was used in a frequency sweep test with a frequency ranging from 1 to 10 Hz. Values of elastic (G') and viscous (G'') modulus were obtained and the results were expressed as value $\tan \delta = G''/G'$ (Mezger, 2002) evaluated on the average frequency. Creep-recovery measurements were conducted in the linear viscoelastic region by imposing a sudden-step shear stress (between 0.1 and 1 Pa) for 60 s in the creep phase. In the recovery phase, sample was allowed to rest for 180 s after stress removal in order to recover the elastic (instantaneous and retarded) part of the deformation. The four-element Burgers model described by the Eq. (2) for the creep phase and Eq. (3) for the recovery phase was used to analyse the obtained creep-recovery curves.

$$J(t) = J_0 + J_1[1 - \exp(-t/\lambda)] + t/\eta_0 \quad (3)$$

$$J(t) = J_{max} - J_0 - J_1[1 - \exp(-t/\lambda)] \quad (4)$$

where J_0 (1/Pa) represents the instantaneous compliance, J_1 (1/Pa) is the retarded elastic compliance or viscoelastic compliance, J_{max} (1/Pa) is maximum compliance, λ (s) is mean retardation time and η_0 (Pa s) is Newtonian viscosity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dynamic oscillatory test results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC), apple fibre (AF) and water levels on viscoelastic properties of gluten-free batters

Trial	HPMC (%)	AF (%)	Water (%)	Viscoelastic properties		
				Crossover $G'=G''$ (Pa)	Crossover frequency (Hz)	$\tan \delta$
1	2	3	190	-	-	1.27±0.06
2	4	3	190	153.75±21.15	1.56±0.34	-
3	2	7	190	82.83±18.77	2.38±0.98	-
4	4	7	190	-	-	0.66±0.01
5	2	5	180	-	-	0.68±0.002
6	4	5	180	-	-	0.68±0.007
7	2	5	200	-	-	1.20±0.07
8	4	5	200	-	-	0.75±0.004
9	3	3	180	-	-	0.77±0.006
10	3	7	180	-	-	0.80±0.02
11	3	3	200	195.00±13.60	1.90±0.36	-
12	3	7	200	-	-	0.86±0.009
13	3	5	190	-	-	0.79±0.02
14	3	5	190	122.1±3.50	1.44±0.09	-
15	3	5	190	-	-	0.81±0.04

Mean values ± standard deviation of three replicates.

Increasing HPMC and AF content at constant water level induced an increase in dynamic moduli with a more pronounced effect of HPMC (data not shown). The increase of elastic modulus (G') with HPMC addition has been previously reported in the literature (Ronda et al., 2013) and explained by enhanced viscoelastic properties of polysaccharides in the aqueous medium. In the case of AF, according to Matos & Rosell (2013) presence of fibrous ingredients with high water binding ability greatly affects batter consistency. The occurrence of crossover point was observed for trials 2, 3, 11 and 14 (Table 1) at a certain frequency. Crossover appearance at lower frequencies was noticed for the more concentrated formulations with 4% HPMC, 3% AF and 3% HPMC, 5% AF at water content of 190% (trials

2 and 14, Table 1). This shifting is indicating a more elastic response when increasing ingredients concentration as previously reported by Rocha Parra et al. (2015a) for GF batters with apple pomace. In all GF formulations, with the exception of formulations containing 2% HPMC, 3 and 5% AF and 190 and 200% water (trials 1 and 7, Table 1) G' was greater than G'' in the whole range of frequencies suggesting a solid elastic-like behaviour. Therefore, $\tan \delta$, the ratio of G'' to G' , was lower than 1 for trials 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13 and 15 (Table 1). Values of $\tan \delta$ greater than 1 in trials 1 and 7 could be attributed simply to the presence of free water in the system and dilution of constituents (Ronda et al., 2013). A significant decline in $\tan \delta$ was observed with the increase in HPMC content from 2% to 4%, for the same AF and water content (trials 7, 8). The substitution of the hydroxyl groups of cellulose by methoxyl and hydroxypropyl groups increases the affinity to the non-polar phase enhancing the HPMC hydrophilic character (Bell, 1990) further resulting in stiffer GF system and improved batter elasticity. Nevertheless, in trials 5 and 6 due to water restriction increase in HPMC content from 2% to 4% had no effect on $\tan \delta$ since HPMC requires enough water for positive acting on GF batter structure (Ronda et al., 2013). Increase in AF content from 3% to 7% at medium HPMC and low water content (trials 9, 10, Table 1) slightly increased $\tan \delta$ but GF batters still expressed predominant elastic behaviour ($\tan \delta < 1$). Furthermore, increase in water content from 180% to 200% in formulations with 2% HPMC and 5% AF (trials 5, 7, Table 1) induced a significant increase in $\tan \delta$ which is expected since alongside water increase the value of $\tan \delta$ rises.

The coefficients of the second-order polynomial response surface equations for creep-recovery parameters (J_0 , J_{max} and η_0) of GF batters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Regression equation coefficients of the second-order polynomial model for creep-recovery parameters of gluten-free batters

Coefficient	J_0 (1 Pa ⁻¹)	J_{max} (1 Pa ⁻¹)	η_0 (Pa s)
Intercept			
Constant	-30.58	-122.43	6309.84
Linear			
HPMC	0.66*	2.66*	-140.18
AF	-0.06	-0.29	-60.83
WATER	0.31	1.25	-61.15*
Quadratic			
HPMC²	0.03	-	-
AF²	-	-	-
WATER²	-7.67E-04	-3.10E-03	0.15*
Interaction			
HPMC*AF	0.02	0.08	-
HPMC*WATER	-5.15E-03	-0.02	0.78
WATER*AF	-	-	0.32
R²	0.79	0.75	0.78
Lack of fit	0.06	0.06	0.05

*Indicates that coefficients are significant at $P < 0.05$.

HPMC incorporation significantly affected GF batter instantaneous and maximum compliance (statistically significant linear coefficients, Table 2). Increase in HPMC content led to the reduction in J_0 and J_{max} (Figure 1a) indicating higher batter strength and increased resistance to deformation as a consequence of HPMC gel forming ability. Obtained results are in agreement with previous findings of Ronda et al. (2013) conducted for HPMC with the same content of methoxyl and hydroxypropoxyl groups.

Figure 1. Effect of hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC) and water levels on instantaneous compliance (a) and Newtonian viscosity (b) in the creep- recovery test.

Although insignificant, a slight decline in J_0 and J_{max} at medium water level was noticed with AF content increase from 3 to 7% probably due to weak slurry formation. As reported in literature, soluble fibres have the ability to develop viscous solutions. Accordingly, high pectin content with great functionality found in AF (O'Shea et al., 2015) could be potentially responsible for batter structure strengthening. Conversely, increasing water content induced increase in J_0 and J_{max} especially in formulations with low HPMC content (Figure 1a) leading to unwanted higher batter deformation when submitted to a constant stress. The effect of HPMC on Newtonian viscosity was not statistically significant although an increase in η_0 with HPMC content increase was observed (Figure 1b). Conversely, the incorporation of AF in higher amount insignificantly reduced η_0 . Water content was the only parameter with a statistically significant influence on η_0 (significant linear and quadratic coefficient, Table 2, Figure 1b). These results confirm the great role of water in formation of GF formulations with optimal rheological properties especially when hydrocolloids and fibres are presented in the system.

CONCLUSIONS

The presented study reveals that the HPMC and AF application in maize-based GF formulations have a positive effect on GF batter rheological properties. Increase in HPMC and AF content increased the elastic modulus hence the majority of studied GF batters expressed a solid elastic-like behavior. A decrease in compliance values was observed with HPMC and AF content increase resulting in higher batter resistance to deformation. HPMC showed a more dominant effect on GF batter rheological properties than AF. Furthermore, adopting appropriate water content for GF formulations enriched with fibres represent a crucial step in gaining workable GF batter and production of GF bread with acceptable quality properties. The physiological implications of AF in GF bread are not known and need to be further explored in order to provide the desired health benefits for coeliac patients.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported by Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research of the Government of Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia (Project no. 142-451-2445/2018). The authors are also grateful to Milex doo for supplying the starch and J. Rettenmaier & Söhne for supplying the hydroxypropylmethylcellulose and apple fibres.

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